

OM Musical Complex

Aesthetics of technique in the conversion of modern heritage

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OM's conversion was a long and non-linear process. In this article, after a brief historical contextualisation and the genesis of the project, we will attempt to use examples to develop the means of action and the objectives they are trying to achieve. This will provide a succinct framework for the project's methodology.

The OM building has a rich history, deeply linked to the steel industry of Seraing. Completed in 1952 in Ougrée (Liège) and designed in the inter-war period by Liège architect Georges Dedoyard, it is a testament to 20th-century social architecture, linked to industry, but also a showcase for corporate wealth through its prestige and architecture.

OM takes its name from *Ougrée-Marihaye*, a steel company. It was Belgium's leading metallurgical company in the pre-war period, and its importance was international, with exports to a large part of Europe. (Bussiere, 1984).

In the aftermath of the war, the company decided to equip itself with a highly social place, designed to host company parties, medal ceremonies and employee departures. It was decided to build it on the banks of the Meuse, between the B blast furnace of Ougrée and the coking plant, right next to the workers' homes. The banquet hall was therefore part of an urban complex defined by the way the steel industry operated, right at the heart of the workspaces.

The years went by, and the end of the Liège steel industry grew ever closer. The last demonstrations were organised in 1990 before the building was abandoned.

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OM's main hall during the heyday of the Seresian iron and steel industry, it was used for many occasions: medal ceremonies, St. Nicolas celebrations and retirement.

Façade along the Meuse, before work was carried out, Dedoyard's modern formal language, alternating rigour and rhythm, is typical of post-war architecture.

Rear facade, before intervention, the building has been abandoned for years. The façade, the result of the project's plan and cross-section, is built using local and industrial materials.

The building follows in the footsteps of Georges Dedoyard's inter-war modernist designs, with a clear formal link to the General Commissariat Palace at the 1939 International Water Exhibition in Liège, and a use of materials similar to that of the *Sauvenière* baths, built 10 years earlier. However, it expresses a skilful blend of monumental modernism, common in post-war reconstructions, and the streamline moderne style. It also borrows elements of language from the projects of Dedoyard's former teacher, Joseph Moutschen (Van Loo, 2003; Houbart, 2014).

The design of the building takes clearly account of the context, with the different spaces subtly arranged to follow the relief of the land; a diagonal circulation of the floor plan sequences the whole and defines the entrance as well as the main façade, which opens out towards the city. The building appears distinguished, with its curved ashlar façade, fine ironwork details and geometric composition. In the interior of the block, however, it is an architecture based on industrial construction methods and language that takes its place. The main hall is undoubtedly the finest example, with a load-bearing structure of slag bricks supporting a metal framework. The façades are rational, with full-height openings between the load-bearing parts of the framework, and the volumes adapted to the functions. Only a light border of red brick dresses the play of volume resulting from the expression of functions and plan.

OM is part of a much more ambitious overall project to heal and even revitalize the wounds left by the death of the steel industry.

Plan of the first floor. The broken circulation links the public space to the two halls and the main vertical circulation.

In the early 2000s, the town of Seraing introduced an ambitious masterplan based on its industrial past. The city embarked on a wave of acquisitions of derelict buildings, including the OM. In 2014, the call for submissions was launched for the first project in the Ougrée-Meuse section of this masterplan, a new district dedicated to youth and culture. Today, OM is part of a much more ambitious overall project, still under construction, which is attempting to heal and even revitalise the wounds left by the death of the steel industry. It is no longer alone in this new hub, with the new pedestrian-bicycle footbridge (arch: AgwA) at the end of the rue de la gare linking it to the recently reopened 125A railway line and the renovated ateliers centraux (arch: Baumans-Deffet). Student accommodation will soon be built in the neighbouring Trassenster Park (archs: atelierchora & Jasper-Eyers) and EGAU's Ougrée town hall will be renovated (arch: Canevas - architects and engineers). This complex, located on the edge of the new urban boulevard, forms a counterpoint to the historic centre of Seraing, a new urban hub. But OM's operations and future depend on this development, and it cannot survive isolated and disconnected as it did before. Over and above its programming and the cultural ambitions it individually embodies, OM is the cornerstone of strong urban and social visions. In this sense, it expresses the direction that the urban and social revitalisation of the town of Seraing is taking, that of rebuilding on its rich industrial past while adapting it to the *Zeitgeist* and making it sustainable over time.

The call for submissions issued for the refurbishment set out clear objectives for the project: adapting the existing building to current standards (special techniques, accessibility, acoustics, tightness, energy performance, Fire conformity) and enhancing the building (exterior lighting, façade restoration). The demand was mainly technical: the building had to be able to live in our time, so it had to be equipped. At first sight, architecture doesn't have much of a place, except for the sensitivity of what's already there.

Imprint left by the dismantling of a glazed ceramic. The study and dismantling of the building highlighted the unique, local character of the original construction.

Our work as architects, and not as technicians, therefore starts with these two questions: how can we adapt this building while preserving its intrinsic qualities? Or: How can the building absorb all the demand without losing its way?

Of course, a programme accompanies this general request. However, it remains fairly basic and is, for the most part, a reworking of the original program. The request was for a main concert hall, a secondary hall, a lounge bar area on the ground floor, and a refurbishment of the sanitary facilities. It was subsequently extended to include recording studios, office spaces and dressing rooms for artists. However, despite this seemingly similar program, the request that the music complex be for amplified music is not insignificant.

The glass roof, made up of multiple points of light, was the central element in the transition from the public space to the performance rooms. It also reinforced the liner atmosphere common at mid-century.

As a result, all the wall compositions will have to be reviewed to guarantee the peace and quiet of the neighbourhood.

Starting with the stated objectives and requirements, a technical analysis of the building is conducted. Coupled with our convictions about conserving the building's qualities and features, the means of action then emerge. As a result, some elements cannot be conserved because their technical characteristics do not allow it (stability or too advanced state of deterioration) or because restoring them to a permanent state is financially unviable. So, we opt for a replacement, a reinterpretation, using contemporary techniques. This applies, for example, to the constellation of light points in the entrance area, which has been rebuilt as it was before.

Conservation was impossible for technical and budgetary reasons. Its identical reconstruction was chosen rather than its replacement by another formal expression.

This raises the question of the authenticity of these elements. We would like to point out that OM was not undergoing heritage restoration and, above all, that financial constraints did not allow this. So, we tried to preserve the spatial qualities, the subtleties, and sensitivities of what already existed. It is a form of accepted compromise: as replacement is inevitable, we have chosen to get closer to what was.

For other elements that require intervention but that do not jeopardise the proper implementation of the project, budgetary constraints mean that it must be postponed. In this case, a protective position is taken so that it can be dealt with later.

But it is conservation that is favoured, with the necessary adaptation for normative or technical reasons. Conservation is achieved by restoring elements, repairing, cleaning, or re-colouring. Adaptation is achieved by adding elements with a different formal language, but with continuity.

The complete process is characterised by economy of use. Whenever possible, we favour conservation or dismantling for reuse in situ. What's more, we consider existing manufactured materials to be unique elements, the result of resource extraction and the work of craftsmen, bearing witness to a history, and which we should take care of as much as possible. This project is a perfect example of this; the judicious use of local materials and metalwork makes it even more deeply rooted in its context.

In the second room, the original parquet flooring is carefully dismantled, repaired, treated, and reinstalled to preserve the ambience and history of the place. The same applies to the bar.

Red, a fiery color

In addition to the work carried out on the existing building, the adaptation of the building also requires the integration of techniques, and the modification or necessary addition of elements to adjust the circulation flows. These elements are varied, but essentially stem from special techniques (ventilation, lighting, sanitary facilities, acoustics). Very quickly, the possibility of integrating all these techniques and adapting the circulation within the existing building envelope was ruled out. The building's capacity to absorb these inputs is limited by its insufficient surface area, but also by the quality of the existing spaces, which would be greatly impacted. Interventions can then only be carried out by adding elements to the building, visible from the public space.

The integration of all these technical elements was based on *complementary* and *additional* aesthetics. In other words, the choice was made not to hide or imitating the existing building, but to develop an identity of its own. It therefore blends into the original building, emerging here and there, and expressing the renewal of the site.

Complementary, because we are constantly seeking a dialogue with what already exists, and our interventions are integrated into the continuity of the existing plan and space, as an extension of the original project. The aesthetic break occurs in the formal and chromatic expression of the elements, not in their integration. In this way, we also see

it as additional, adding an expression, a language to the building.

In this addition, made up of a multitude of technical elements, we consciously limit the diversity to promote the intelligibility of the intervention. So, we chose a single colour, red, which preserves the heterogeneity of the materials and formal writing of the added elements while creating a coherent intervention. With this ensemble, we are also reinforcing the urban impact and changing the identity of the building. The choice of colour is inspired by the history of the site, the image of the flame burning at the top of the blast furnace, the fiery colour of the region, the one the steel industry.

A coherent set of *additional* and *complementary* interventions

Here we develop examples by type of intervention, both modifying and adding, ranging from finishing details to adding volume. In this way, the work transcends scale, while at the same time attempting to interact with the urban landscape and the finesse of the existing ironwork.

Installation of the upper walkway, linking the office areas to the new roof terrace.

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1. Technical installation in capable spaces 2. Work in the cellar 3. Technical integration in main hall 4. Exterior facade of main hall with red brick edging 5. Reinforcement of studio floor 6. Dismantling of second hall floor 7. Assembly of walkways in workshop 8. Installation of walkways on site

Technology serves as a support for the materialization of discourse.

The layout of the roof elements goes beyond what has already been mentioned. In fact, as well as being a technical protection intervention that is part of the whole, their positioning, their shapes and above all their changing perception (red at night, white on sunny days, almost imperceptible on cloudy days) make them a new urban landmark and mark the public but also recreational aspect of the site. Not that the existing building did not already assert these urban and public aspects, but that it was necessary to reaffirm them, to signify its renewal. Its presence is then once again marked on a large scale, proclaiming its function, the relocation of the site, and a form of renaissance. Technology serves as a support for the materialisation of the discourse; it also serves the perception of architecture but also, we must be aware, political and communications ambitions.

So, like all technical interventions in the building, the ambition is twofold. To respond to a need and to communicate and interact with the users and the existing architecture.

Their positioning, shapes and, above all, their changing perception make the technique a new urban landmark and mark the public and recreational aspects of the site.

At night, the Meuse River acts as a mirror, reinforcing the building's presence in the public space. The building then fully expresses its urbanity, its role as a landmark in the landscape.

The addition of external circulation elements stems from a number of constraints: the need to connect spaces more directly, make previously inaccessible areas accessible, and provide access to outdoor areas and terraces. We see these constraints as technical: we need to connect point A to point B. The exterior walkway was chosen as the least costly solution, and above all one that allows direct expression of circulation. These do not alter the heated volume, thus also limiting operating costs. They are located on the rear facade, clarifying as much as they blur its operation.

Like the formal expression of the rear façade's technical features, the walkways are limited to their own structure and user protection, with color as the only covering, linking them to the red brick façade bands.

Relativity by Maurits Cornelis Escher - Chaotic traffic organization.

CHAPTER 4 STRUCTURES AND CONSTRUCTIONS

The walkway leading from the entrance to the courtyard designed by Ney&Partners . This walkway expresses itself as a direct link to the outside world, an invitation to enter as much as to go outside. Its design is the result of a succession of open porticoes, a formal expression of internal efforts.

In the manner of Escher’s “Relativity”, these links seem to hang together chaotically in an equally chaotic space. Yet the choreography they form is a direct result of the broken plan of the whole, and merely adds to or extends the circulations on an already existing node. In this way, they represent the continuity of the rear façade’s compositional principles and the way it functions in plan and cross-section, but also a break with a later intervention, expressed as follows.

The balustrade of the lounge bar was raised, preserving the element's original appearance while doubling it, thus creating a double interpretation - that of a whole, but also of an addition.

Less visibly, technical replacements had to be made. These demolitions and reconstructions of parts of the original building are purely technical. The only constraint we impose on ourselves in these circumstances is that they should have as negligible impact as possible on the perception of the building, unlike additions, which modify it.

Floors were replaced to support recording studios that were too heavy for the existing structure; ceilings were replaced to support scenography equipments. These sometimes unexpected technical challenges mean that, as architects, we must not set aside our primary ambitions of preserving and enhancing our heritage.

As mentioned above, we generally went for a position of preservation and addition rather than replacement, in the same vein as overall integrations. We cannot deny that this choice modifies the aesthetics of the element in question, but we do try to induce a double reading of it, making it unique and double at the same time.

Here we explore the case of balustrades, where the introduction of safety standards requires work to be carried out, essentially raising the height of the balustrade. The main uprights are doubled, and the fastening of the new but common upright takes on a purely technical form, contrasting with the invisibility of the welding of the existing upright but playing with the massiveness of the latter's details. From distance, they form a single unit; up close, they are doubled, yet one depends on the other.

As standards and attitudes evolve, it is necessary to make the building accessible to all. The walkways help to achieve this, but are not enough, so two elevators has been added. Unlike the choices made for the integration of rooftop technology or walkways, the elevators are installed within the existing envelope. However, it expresses themselves in the same way as the above-mentioned elements. But here, the intervention takes a back seat; unlike the others, which cohabit with the existing without subtracting from it, this one clearly leaves the original facade as the first reading. As for the rest, the existing is preserved, while the new is added, here in the background. This is the only expression on the façade of the building's adaptation, which results from the need for direct access from the pub-

lic space and the most optimal distribution. The building's visibility derives from its operation and needs, but is assumed and expressed like everything else, although with a slight restraint.

In the end, we're trying to develop what we might call an aesthetic with a constant double language, built largely on technical responses. A form of aesthetics of technique (de Beaune & Hilaire-Pérez, 2012). We'll conclude with these few words: the success of the project and its ambitions can only be achieved thanks to the flexibility of all those involved, and the establishment of a sound relationship based on clearly defined, shared objectives.

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